

Performance of broadcast seeded TM8089

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TM8089 is a high-yielding blast-tolerant red rice selection from TKM9. It was isolated at the Paddy Experiment Station, Tirur, to replace highly blast-susceptible TKM9. We compared TM8089, which is suitable for rainfed lowland cultivation, and TKM9 broadcast seeded and transplanted in 200-m² observational plots.

Broadcast seeding was at 100 kg seed/ha. Transplanting was at 60 kg seed/ha. Thinning and gap filling were done in the broadcast plots; transplanting was at 2 to 3

Comparison of TM8089 and TKM9 broadcast and transplanted.^a Tamil Nadu, India.

Character	Broadcast seeding		Transplanting		
	TKM9	TM8089	TKM9	TM8089	TM8089
Plant height (cm)	93.8	95.2	99.0	(5.696)**	103.6
Productive tillers	5.0	5.0	10.4	(4.472)**	10.6
Panicle length (cm)	20.6	(1.963)**	18.6	(6.321)**	22.4
Panicle weight (g)	3.0	3.0	3.0	(8.179)**	3.2
Grains/panicle	71.0	(2.855)**	76.0	(4.989)**	97.0
Yield (t/ha)	2.6	3.1	5.0		5.2
Difference (%)	-	17.5	-		5.5

^at values in parentheses are highly significant.

seedlings/hill, 15- × 10-cm spacing. Management practices were common for both planting treatments.

Twenty hills were selected at random from each plot and plant height, productive tillers, panicle length, panicle weight, and grains/panicle were recorded. Differences between direct seeding and transplanting were distinct

(see table). All traits were lower under broadcast seeding, in particular, number of productive tillers.

TM8089 was better than TKM9 in all traits except panicle length. Its higher yield is attributed to more grains per panicle under broadcast seeding and to more grains per panicle and higher panicle weight under transplanting. □

Cross compatibility between Guizhou traditional upland sinica varieties and short-statured indica varieties

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Cross compatibility between 296 Guizhou traditional upland sinica varieties and 3 short-statured indica varieties was tested in 663 F₁ combinations in 1985.

A number of the local upland sinicas have high cross compatibility with short-statured indicas. The upland sinicas have higher cross compatibility with the short-statured indicas than with lowland sinicas (Table 1). They also have distinctly higher cross compatibility with short-statured Guichao 2 than with common short-statured sinicas (Table 2). The high and low cross compatibility between sinicas and indicas are negatively correlated with the latitudes and elevations of the origins of the sinicas and positively with mean temperature and >10 °C cumulative 1-yr temperature of the places of origin. The closest relationship is with latitude. □

Table 1. Distribution of cross compatibility (CC) between Guizhou upland sinica varieties and short-statured indica varieties. China, 1985.

Male parent	Total (no.)	>50% CC		>60% CC		>70% CC		>80% CC		>90% CC	
		no.	%	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%
Lowland rice	545	294	53.94	151	27.71	55	10.09	11	2.02		
Upland rice	118	81	68.64	45	33.14	22	18.64	9	7.63	3	2.5
Total	663	375	56.56	196	29.26	77	11.61	20	3.02	3	0.45

Table 2. CC of short-statured Guichao 2 with local upland sinica and common short-statured sinica rice varieties.

Male parent	F ₁ distribution (no.)			F ₁ CC		
	Total	> 60% CC	170% CC	Highest	Lowest	Mean
Local upland sinica	22	2	1	72.52	30.63	49.90
Common short-statured sinica	24	0	0	50.36	10.87	33.69

Varieties suitable for direct seeding in the Ganges floodplain

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The Ganges River floodplain, formed through soil erosion and deposits, is estimated to total 0.24 million ha. The land is subjected to periodical flooding

in the wet season and crops are generally grown in the winter season.

With the introduction of bamboo boring, another crop in the stabilized floodplain in the summer season before flooding has become possible.

As a short-duration summer rice crop after winter crop harvest, transplanted, irrigated Pusa 2-21 and Pusa 33 performed well and were harvested before flooding started. But summer rice